

Two modes of operation can be defined for the SFC using the complementary controlled solid state switches, S1 and S2. These two switches follow NOT LOGIC command. That is, while S1 is on, S2 is off and vice versa. Configuration of the proposed SFC is shown in Fig.1.

III. CONTROL STRUCTURE

There are two type controllers in the proposed system. Fig. 2 shows SFC-power filter controller using a dynamic tracking regulator with three loops. The first loop is a voltage regulator that tracks reference voltage ($V_m\text{-ref}$). The second and third loops are dynamic type error tracking loops to stabilize current variations and limit any sudden power excursions, respectively.

The second controller loop is used to controller the energy flow from the PV-Solar array via the VSI-6 pulse inverter and De-Ac interface as shown in Fig. 3 using the photovoltaic current, photovoltaic voltage and photovoltaic power inputs. Every input error is obtained by taking the difference between the real and delayed real input values. The photovoltaic voltage r , the photovoltaic error and the photovoltaic power errors are multiplied by the selected weighting factors (I_γ , v_γ and p_γ) and the output summations is a total Tri-loop error. The tri-loop error is multiplied by a weight factor K_h .

This will ensure time-descaling and weighting of the auxiliary loops.

Fig. 2 Switched Power filter SFC-Dynamic Controller

Fig. 3 PV-Inverter VSI-6 Pulse Dynamic Controller

The global output signal of the dynamic error driven controller is followed by a modified Weighted-Modified PID (WMPID) controller displayed in Fig. 4. WMPID includes an error sequential activation supplementary loop, ensuring fast dynamic response and effective damping of large excursions,

in addition to conventional PID structure. Moreover, the output signal of the Weighted Modified PID controller enters a PWM signal generator. On-off switching sequences produced by PWM define two operating modes of the FACTS device of SFC and PV-hybrid system.

Fig. 4 Modified weighted PID controller with additional error squared compensating/dynamic accelerating loop

IV. STUDY SYSTEM

The sample study AC grid network with the PV array interface is shown in Fig. 5. It comprises a local hybrid load (linear, nonlinear and induction motor type loads) and is connected to an infinite bus through 6 km transmission line. The unified AC system, SFC-filter/compensator and the controller parameters are given in Tables I and II, respectively.

Fig. 5 Study System

V. RESULTS

To validate the FACTS SFC Scheme dynamic stabilization and efficient energy utilization with proposed control schemes for stabilization of the host smart grid under short and open circuit condition, the MATLAB/Simulink Software Environment was utilized in all digital simulation, a 3-phase short circuit in middle bus is applied at time 0.02 sec of the AC grid, and it is cleared after 0.02 sec. The results of the simulation under short circuit condition in PV bus and load bus has been shown in Figs. 6-11 and Figs 12-17, respectively. Moreover, open circuit dynamic simulation results for load bus are shown in Figs.18-23. Additionally, all parameters of the elements which are used in simulation are mentioned in Appendix A and B. The FACTS SFC scheme was validated to be effective in stabilizing bus voltages, improving power factor and reducing inrush currents under short and open circuit faults in the case study.

Fig. 6 RMS voltage waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 11 Apparent power waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 7 RMS Current waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 12 RMS voltage waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 8 Active power waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 13 RMS current waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 9 Reactive power waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 14 Active power waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 10 Power Factor waveform in PV bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 15 Reactive power waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 16 Power factor waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 21 Reactive power waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

Fig. 17 Apparent waveform in load bus under short circuit operation

Fig. 22 Power factor waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

Fig. 18 RMS voltage waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

Fig. 23 Apparent power waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

Fig. 19 RMS current waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

Fig. 20 Active power waveform in load bus under open circuit operation

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel switched/modulated power filter compensator (SFC) scheme. The FACTS based switched/Modulated Filter-capacitor compensator with the proposed dynamic controllers using time-descaled tri-loop error driven regulation and a modified-weighted PID Controller. The digital simulation results validated the SFC FACTS Scheme for effective AC system stabilization, power factor improvement, voltage stabilization, power factor correction and power quality enhancement. The proposed FACTS based SFC-Filter/compensator scheme can be extended to other applications using distributed/dispersed renewable energy interface and green energy utilization systems and easily modified for other control objectives such as feeder loss reduction and DSM-demand side Management in addition to voltage stabilization and efficient utilization. Other applications include V2H/V2G Battery charging schemes using hybrid PV-NG Powered Fuel Cell and smart grid AC-DC Interface.

TABLE I
THE AC SYSTEM AND SFC-FILTER PARAMETERS

Transmission Line	25 Kv (L-L), 6km R/Km=0.35 Ω, L/Km=0.4 Mh	
Infinite Bus	138 Kv, X/R=10	
SFC	$C_s=14\mu\text{f}$, $C_{s1}=14\mu\text{f}$, $C_{sh1}=225\mu\text{f}$ $R_f=0.15\Omega$, $L_f=3\text{mh}$	
Local Hybrid Ac Load	Induction Motor	0.2 Mva, 4 Poles $R_s=0.01965\text{pu}$, $L_s=0.0397\text{ Pu}$ $R_r=0.01909\text{pu}$, $L_r=0.0397\text{ Pu}$ $L_m=1.354\text{ Pu}$
	Linear Load	$P=0.1\text{ Mw}$, $Q=0.043\text{ Mvar}$
	Nonlinear Load	0.1 Mva, $\text{Pf}=0.9$
PV-Hybrid System	Photovoltaic Cell	$V_{\text{out}}=1600\text{v}$, $P_{\text{out}}=1\text{mw}$
	Battery	Lithium-Ion, 1600v, 1750ah, S.O.C 10%
Power Transformer	T_1	138/25kv, 5 Kva
	T_2	25/4.16kv, 5 Kva
	T_3	25/1.6kv, 1 Kva

TABLE II
THE CONTROLLER PARAMETERS

Device	Value
PV-Hybrid Scheme	$R_0=R_b=0.5$, $L_0=R_b=0.05\text{mh}$, $C_0=1275\text{mf}$
PV Controller Gains	$K_e=1$, $K_p=25$, $K_i=2$, $K_d=1$, PWM Frequency $F_s=1750\text{ Hz}$
SFC Controller Gains	$K_e=1$, $K_p=25$, $K_i=2$, $K_d=1$, PWM Frequency $F_s=2500\text{ Hz}$
LC Filter	$L=0.1\text{mh}$, $R=0.5\Omega$, $C=200\text{mf}$

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